

Application of Seebeck and Peltier Effect in Radiological Imaging

Jihyeon Yoon*(Korean medicine doctor, flyingtext@nate.com)

December 22, 2022

Abstract

By given equation in Fermi-Dirac statistics, three types of energy diffusion could be released into form of wave when ensembles of particles are scattered. By extending this approach, Peltier effect would be revisited in an explanation of heat. And speaking of heat, electromagnetic imaging by energy scattered in form of waves would be revisited with Seebeck effect.

1 Introduction

As discussed earlier in ensembles of energy within CPT approach[Yoon(2022a)][Yoon(2022b)], three types of probabilistic approach could be related in one single decomposition of energy.

$$\begin{aligned} (LFO \text{ Chain}) &\equiv (CPT \text{ Conservation}) \\ \implies Z_i(N)/Z_i(N-1) &= e^{-\mu/k_B T} = \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1\right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\varepsilon_i/k_B T}} \\ \implies \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1\right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\varepsilon_i/k_B T}} - \frac{1}{e^{\mu/k_B T}} + 1 &= 1 \\ \implies \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1\right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{(\varepsilon_i - \mu)/k_B T}} - 1 + e^{\mu/k_B T} &= e^{\mu/k_B T} \\ \implies \left(\left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1\right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\varepsilon_i/k_B T}} + 1\right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{-\mu/k_B T}} - 1 &= e^{\mu/k_B T} \\ \implies \left(\left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1\right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\varepsilon_i/k_B T}} - 1\right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{-\mu/k_B T}} - 1 &= -e^{\mu/k_B T} \end{aligned}$$

While upper discussion could be an extension of what has been discussed in precedent fusion and fission, situation in observation gives an assumption that $\alpha = 1 - PE(E)$, $\beta = 1 - ME(E)$, and $\gamma = 1 - OE(E)$ [Yoon(2022b)]:

$$\begin{aligned} LFO \cdot (\alpha + \alpha\beta + \alpha\beta\gamma) &= 1 \\ \alpha + \beta &= 1 - \gamma \end{aligned}$$

And by definition of PE [Yoon(2022b)]:

*Jihyeon Yoon is a korean medicine doctor. And he is a freelancer programmer also.
Yeongdeungpo-gu, Seoul, 07429,
Seoul, South Korea
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9610-0994>
Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100007799947263>

$$\begin{aligned}
1 - \gamma &= LFO \\
\implies (\alpha + \beta)\alpha(1 + \beta + \beta\gamma) &= 1 \\
\implies 1 + \beta + \beta\gamma &= \frac{1}{(\alpha + \beta)\alpha} \\
\implies 1 &= \frac{1}{(\alpha + \beta)\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{\beta} - \gamma \\
\implies \gamma &= \frac{1}{\beta} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha(\alpha + \beta)} - 1 \right) - 1
\end{aligned}$$

While given the definitions of observation biases,

References

- [Yoon(2022a)] Jihyeon Yoon. Nuclear Fusion Framework for Simulating Universe. Technical report, Zenodo, November 2022a. URL <https://zenodo.org/record/7317555>.
- [Yoon(2022b)] Jihyeon Yoon. Descriptive Method in Spatiotemporal Simulation Observation. Technical report, Zenodo, December 2022b. URL <https://zenodo.org/record/7430238>.